

EWA-BELT

Linking East and West African farming systems experience
into a BELT of sustainable intensification

Introducing Fonio in the Farming systems to enhance Food Security and Incomes in Northern Ghana and Burkina Faso

Practice Abstract n.1

Authors: James Kombiok (1), Rachele Stentella (2), Margherita Rizzu (3)

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The EWA-BELT Project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon2020 research and innovation programme under agreement No 862848

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Given its early maturing stage and nutritious nature, Fonio (*Digitaria Exilis* (Kippist) Stapf) has been known as an important food security crop in the growing areas since it closes the hunger gap between the planting and harvesting period of the major staple crops such as maize. However, nowadays its production is being neglected in many areas of West Africa and no improved varieties are currently available. Kundok Development Consult as part of the EWA-BELT project has introduced and evaluated Fonio production in four Ghanaian districts (Savelugu, West Mamprusi, Talensi and Nabdam) testing four local varieties (Namba, Nnamba, Wagadugu and Nfonikpa). Since Nnamba resulted the highest yielding landrace (~900–1000 kg ha⁻¹), it was proposed to 20 farmer groups in the 4 districts, for a total of 400 farmers, which have been linked to a processor company. Furthermore, five farmers per each district, representing each group, will be trained with a Training of Trainers (ToT) approach on the manual processing of the crop so that by the end of the project, a total of 100 farmers (25 per district) will produce Fonio. On these premises, not only the inclusion of Fonio in the farming systems will have the capability to enhance food security, but also, if produced in larger quantities than farmers own consumption, it could be sold to the mechanical processing company also increasing the farmers' household income. Within the project, the partner ACRA also directed part of its research on Fonio, assessing two different crop management practices in the areas of Zorgho, Loumbila and Guié in Burkina Faso. Preliminary results showed a yield increase of about 124% (830 kg ha⁻¹) under manure fertilization (60 kg ha⁻¹) and deeply row-seeding compared to the traditional practices with no fertilizer and broadcasting sowing (370 kg ha⁻¹).

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Ayi lihi di ni bi yuuri ka biri shɛm, n-ti pahi di ni tiri ninsali ningbun' alaafɛe shɛm, zinzam nyɛla puzuri shɛli din ni tooi gu ka che bindirigu kalinsi bee bindir' pooli luy'shɛŋa bɛ ni kɔri li, dɔmi, di tooi biri la saha shɛli bɛ ni biriti bindir' kpana kamani kawana, n zaŋ hali ni di kpuyibu saha. Amaa saha shɛŋa ti ni Ɔiya ŋɔ, zinzam kɔbu nyɛla bɛ ni dii bi kpaŋsi shɛli Afirika wulin luhili bɔba ni di yaya ni, ka zinzam balibu din ti tooni gba kani. Kumdok lɛbigimsim tuma yili nim yay'shɛli bɛ ni bɔli EWA-BELT la nyɛla ban zaŋ zinzam kɔbu n-wuhi pukpariba ti Gana ŋɔ yaya anahi, ka zahin di kɔbu n-nya din chaŋ shɛm yaya anahi maa ni. Lala yaya maa n-nyɛ Savelugu, Mamprugu wulin luhili, Talinsi ni Nabdom n-ti pahi di bɔba ni di yaya. Yaya anahi ŋɔ nyɛla ban buyisi zinzam ni mali bal' shɛŋa kɔbu, di ni n-nyɛ Namba, Nnamba , Wagadugu n-ti pahi Nfonikpa.

Buyisibu ŋɔ ni, zinzam bal'shɛli bɛ ni bɔli Nnamba la n daa niŋ viɛnyɛlinga n-gari di taba maa zaa. Yika ayi ni pirigili kam puuni, Nnamba daa kpuyila kpalinsi awɔi zan chaŋ kpalan pia polo.

Dinzuɣu, bɛ daa zaŋ Nnamba balibu maa n-ti pukpariba layinsi pishi, Gana yaya anahi shɛŋa bɛ ni daa pii la, ka pukpariba maa zaa daa yiyisi kɔbishinahi. Bɛ daa lahi bɔla tuma yili shɛli ban mali mashina din maani zinzam ŋɔ, ka bɛ mini pukpariba maa pɔha daa yooi taba, din yɛn che ka pukpariba maa yi ti kpuyi zinzam maa, ka bɛ zaŋ bɛ mashina maa m- mali li viɛnyɛlinga.

Din lahi pahi, bɛ daa pii la pukpariba anu yaya yini kam puuni, ni bɛ ti ba baŋsim zaŋ kpa zinzam malibu polo, di yi ti ko n-kpuyi, ka baŋsim ŋɔ nyɛla bɛ zaŋ na n-ti wuhi bɛ pukparitaba. Ka di daliri nyɛla bɛ ti yɛn wuligi baŋsim maa n-gili zaa, pukpariba kɔbga n-yɛn mali lala baŋsim maa. Ka yayili kam mali pukpariba pishi ni anu, ban mali baŋsim ŋɔ.

Di pala ti yi zaŋ zinzam kɔbu m-pahi ti pukparilim ni ko n-yɛn gu ka che bindir' pooli bee bindirigu kalinsi, amaa bɛ yi tooi kɔri li pam n-yayiri dibu zuɣu, bɛ ni kɔhiri di shɛli ka liyiri maa gba sɔŋ pukpariba maa ka bɛ tooi gbub bɛ dundɔna.

Vihigu zaŋ kpa zinzam kɔbu polo nyɛla tuma yili shɛli ti ni bɔli ACRA, ni zaŋ shɛli chaŋ ti paai Burikina tinsi ata, ka bɛ yuya booni Zorgho, Loumbila ni Guie, ni bɛ buyisi zinzam kɔbu paya paya maa shɛŋa. Vihigu maa wuhiya ni di daa niŋ viɛnyɛla pam. Vihigu maa laha wuhiya ni zinzam kpalansi di baa wɔi n-daa yina yika ayi ni pirigili puuni, bɛ ni daa zaŋ binkɔb bina ka mani kpalan kabli m-bahi pushɛŋa, ka lahi zaŋ zinzam shɛŋa din nyɛ zaɣ' kahi-bima m-biri. Ka zinzam kpalansi anahi laasabu mi n-daa yina pushɛŋa ban daa bi doli pukparilim so' pala la shɛli, yika ayi ni pirigili kam puuni.

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Kiu (Fonio) Koob la yõndo koom guidgrē la Koosūm yõndo Ghana (Nord) la Burkina Faso

Kiu wa sē bīit Tūlga là sē ya rīib sē tūin koom Ed mī-yē Koob yõndo kakūadba yīinga.kiu tūē songamē tid toi kom yemmdē. Bala a buiūg saasa Ti Kamana nē koodā taaba nā ka taayé(kiu tūē yiilim doogo). Nēeba wūusg yaoülē la miin-yé bon la koodā wūusg yé. Kiu bises sē bēe ka bīs tūulūlg yé.

Kundok Développent consul tūum wēgīn (projet EWA BELT) ūb nāanga kiu wa Koob nē Ghana temsā naas sē zoé koo niin kood bois toētoēya (Savelugu, west mamprusi,talensi, la nabdam) lab nāanga kiu kood bīs sē ya sōmbo n-yīida tāaba (900–1000 kg ha–1) id riika kiu bīs bamba n-nāanga Koob tēmssa naz puusē nē kakūadb bamba kobs nassé sē pūui saas piisī. Teng fāa tūumda nēeba nū Saas piisī wā pūugē tid nā zams ba (kōnb bangrē)kiū Koob wēgē ti tuubda (projet) bassego kadūadb baam kūabga (kakūadb pīsī-la-nū teng fāa) nā kiinba kiu wā. Kitamē ti kood kang na sōngamē tiib tong koom lab koosé m paam yõndo kiu wā koosg pūugē ā bīs wūuslem kiēlem.

"Projet" kang pūugē Accra Burkina tūum taaga lūissa toogo Ghana kiu bīs koob naangr Burkina nīn būdbā la koomb māansiim tūētūēya (zorgho, loumbila nē Guié Burkina solmē). Rē vinēgamē ti māansiim bamba sōmblom yīida Burkina kakūadba būdbā nakingrē. Bamb dīnga ya 124% (830 ha–1, nē pōnsg 60kg ha–1) ti Burkina kakūadba sē miinimē bütē (370 kg ha–1, bamb pā niingd pōnsg yē).

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